

AI-Based Techniques for Condition Monitoring and Rotor Fault Detection in Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors: A Review

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Abstract—This study provides a comparative review of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques for condition monitoring and rotor fault detection in Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs). Machine Learning (ML) has gained prominence across diverse domains, including electrical machines, for enhancing motor performance, minimizing downtime, and enabling predictive maintenance. These advancements yield significant cost savings, extend operational lifespans, and improve machine safety. Early detection of rotor faults is critical, as their occurrence adversely impacts PMSM performance. While existing studies have primarily focused on ML applications for demagnetization and eccentricity faults, research on rotor fault detection, diagnosis, and monitoring in PMSMs remains limited. Consequently, AI-based condition monitoring requires further development to achieve robust rotor fault detection and diagnosis. This paper systematically reviews traditional and AI-based methodologies employed in current research, highlighting gaps and future directions.

Index Terms—Monitoring, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Faults in Rotor, diagnosis, Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors.

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of PMSMs in recent years has significantly advanced electric motor technology. Their advantages include high efficiency, power density, compact size, and torque density. Advanced permanent magnet (PM) materials create a concentrated magnetic field within the air gap minimizing volume and weight while allowing optimized designs for industrial and transportation applications [1], [2]. Similar to other electromechanical machines, PMSMs are vulnerable to various damages, including magnetic faults (demagnetization of PM), mechanical faults (bearing issues, rotor misalignment, and eccentricity), and electrical faults (stator winding faults) [2]. Prompt diagnosis and detection of these faults are essential to minimize motor damage and performance loss [3]. The reliability, efficiency and longevity of PMSM depend on proper condition monitoring and fault detection. Their importance lies in the ability to detect early signs of mechanical and electrical failures, helping to prevent significant breakdowns and minimize operational disruptions.

A key aspect of condition monitoring is the real-time observation of the motor's operational parameters. Reference [4] emphasizes the need for automated monitoring of demagnetization faults in PMSMs, highlighting that such faults can lead to torque and speed variations that significantly affect control precision. The authors in reference [4] recommend real-time tracking of magnetic flux density variations in PMs to enable timely fault detection and mitigate potential damage.

Incorporation of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) into condition assessment, anomaly detection, and prognostic maintenance systems has fundamentally transformed the operational management of PMSMs. This evolution is attributed to AI's capacity to process large volumes of data, learn from historical trends, and optimize maintenance schedules, which significantly enhances reliability and minimizes operational downtime [5], [6].

This paper describes various rotor faults in PMSMs, and diagnostic signatures; examines AI techniques for rotor fault detection and diagnosis; and discusses condition monitoring methods for PMSM rotor faults; highlighting the available challenges and proposing future research directions to enhance fault detection and diagnosis in PMSMs.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section II gives an overview of rotor faults in PMSMs and the associated diagnostic signals. Section III discusses artificial intelligence in condition monitoring and fault diagnosis, along with AI techniques for rotor fault diagnosis. Section IV addresses condition monitoring strategies using AI. Section V explores future trends and research directions, followed by the conclusion.

II. ROTOR-RELATED FAILURES IN PMSM MACHINES

The study of rotor faults in PMSMs is essential due to the growing use of these motors in various industries, as noted in Section I. Rotor faults, specifically demagnetization and eccentricity, severely affect motor performance, highlighting the need for effective detection and diagnosis techniques. Rotor eccentricity occurs when the rotor is misaligned within the stator, resulting in uneven air-gap spacing that influences

Fig. 1. Rotor Faults in PMSMs

electromagnetic force. Research indicates that rotor eccentricity leads to increased torque oscillations, noise, and vibration while also decreasing motor efficiency [7]–[9]. There are three types of eccentricity: static (occurs when the rotor is permanently displaced from the center of the stator by a fixed distance), dynamic (happens when the rotor’s displacement from the center of the stator changes continuously as the motor rotates), and mixed (a combination of both static and dynamic) [10].

Demagnetization of the rotor’s PMs is another significant fault that changes the motor’s magnetic characteristics. The demagnetization fault can be classified as reversible or irreversible based on recoverability. Reversible demagnetization allows the magnet to regain its strength after temperature reduction without re-magnetization, while irreversible demagnetization means the magnet cannot recover its original strength unless remagnetized [11]. If only a portion (e.g., trailing edges) of the PM loses its magnetic strength, this phenomenon is referred to as “partial demagnetization.” Conversely, uniform demagnetization occurs when all PMs experience a consistent reduction in magnetization, often attributed to fluctuations in temperature [12].

In addition to rotor eccentricity and demagnetization faults, rotor imbalance and misalignment represent significant fault conditions. The imbalance and misalignment of the rotor disrupt the motor’s magnetic field, thereby impairing the machine’s dynamic properties. This disruption leads to the generation of additional components in the mechanical vibration spectrum, raises noise levels, and causes torque fluctuations [2].

Furthermore, Reference [13] concentrated on a fault severity index that evaluates stator winding faults aggravated by rotor issues such as demagnetization. Their findings highlight the relationship between rotor and stator faults, suggesting that a rotor fault can lead to compounded problems in the stator, ultimately affecting overall system reliability [13]. The development of intelligent monitoring systems employing machine

learning algorithms for detecting rotor faults is vital. For example, reference [14] demonstrated the effectiveness of current signature analysis combined with machine learning for diagnosing demagnetization faults [14].

The importance of condition monitoring systems is reinforced by multiple studies, including a recent one by Reference [15], which emphasizes dynamic modeling to assess the impacts of rotor demagnetization alongside eccentricity [15]. This analysis offers insights into the rotor’s behavior under operational stress and potential failures. Additionally, advancements in fault-tolerant control systems will be crucial as designs become more complex; the author’s study in reference [16] illustrated the effectiveness of predictive fault-tolerant control methods in managing performance degradation caused by rotor faults [16]. Conventional techniques for monitoring fault conditions include temperature tracking, acoustic measurement, torque fluctuation analysis, vibration surveillance, and frequency domain evaluation [17]. The detection methods for electrical machines are [17], [18]:

- Signal-based techniques encompass three primary methodologies: Analysis in the frequency domain, time domain, and combined time-frequency domain;
- Model-based techniques encompass three primary methodologies: Analytical approaches, two-dimensional and three-dimensional finite element analysis, and hybrid modeling methods and;
- Artificial techniques encompass the Fuzzy Logic (FL), Decision Trees and Random Forests, Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN), Deep Learning (DL), Expert systems, Hidden Markov Models and Bayesian Networks.

III. AI-DRIVEN APPROACHES FOR FAULT DETECTION AND MONITORING SYSTEM CONDITIONS

A. AI Techniques for Rotor Fault Diagnosis and condition monitoring.

The use of AI for monitoring and fault detection in PMSMs has attracted considerable interest recently, mainly due to the growing dependence on electrical machines in critical applications. AI methodologies enhance fault detection and diagnosis, thereby improving reliability and reducing maintenance costs associated with PMSM operation. Reference [19] proposes an innovative automated detection and classification method integrated into the inverter, effectively addressing the limitations of traditional offline and online monitoring techniques. This method enables real-time monitoring and improves response times to potential faults by using algorithms that analyze stator currents and voltages for diagnostics [19], [20].

Numerous studies have explored AI-driven methods for condition monitoring and fault detection in electrical motors. Machine learning algorithms have become a key focus in diagnosing rotor faults in PMSMs because they excel at processing and analyzing complex signal data patterns more effectively than conventional techniques. Machine learning techniques are typically classified as supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and reinforcement learning [21].

- Supervised learning includes SVM, ANNs, Decision Trees, Random Forests, Similarity Learning, Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression, and k-nearest neighbours (kNN) and Discriminant Analysis.
- Unsupervised learning includes principal component analysis (PCA), isolation forest, k-means clustering, hierarchical clustering, auto-encoders, and fuzzy c-means.
- Semi-supervised learning algorithms include Self-training with Support Vector Machines, Co-training, and Pseudo-labeling.
- Reinforcement Learning algorithms encompass control theory, game theory, genetic algorithms, multi-agent systems, statistics, and Q-learning [18], [21]–[23].

Deep Learning (DL), a subset of ML, employs Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). DL algorithms include autoencoders, convolutional neural networks (CNN), perceptrons, probabilistic neural networks, and recurrent neural networks [18]. Deep learning algorithms have become crucial in diagnosing rotor faults in PMSMs. Their effectiveness lies in processing and classifying fault signals, which is difficult because of the dynamic and noisy characteristics of real-world operational data [24], [25]. The exploration of deep learning techniques has advanced significantly, resulting in notable improvements in fault detection capabilities [26]. Additionally, machine learning frameworks, particularly those using ANNs and SVMs, have shown significant effectiveness in classifying rotor fault conditions. Reference [27] emphasizes that AI-based methods for condition monitoring can reduce maintenance costs and improve operational efficiency, underscoring their importance in industrial applications [27].

The comparative analysis evaluates various AI methodologies employed in rotor fault detection. It demonstrates that machine learning approaches, particularly ANNs and SVMs, have considerable efficacy in early fault detection, particularly concerning eccentricity and demagnetization failures [14], [28]. This effectiveness is attributed to their capacity to process large datasets and discern complex fault patterns. Furthermore, deep learning and hybrid approaches significantly enhance diagnostic accuracy by handling high-dimensional data and multiple simultaneous faults. Combining AI with signal processing methods like continuous wavelet transform (CWT) and sensor fusion enhances real-time monitoring performance and increases system reliability. Nevertheless, challenges persist concerning interpretability and data requirements, underscoring the necessity for ongoing research into robust AI-based fault detection systems [29]. Table I provides a comparison of AI techniques applied to the detection of eccentricity and demagnetization faults: The table I shows the comparative analysis of AI techniques for eccentricity and demagnetization faults:

IV. CONDITION MONITORING STRATEGIES USING MACHINE LEARNING

Modern condition monitoring has evolved over several decades, driven by experience, innovation, and technological advancements. Condition monitoring strategies utilizing ML in

TABLE I
EVALUATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE METHODS FOR ROTOR FAULT DETECTION IN PERMANENT MAGNET SYNCHRONOUS MOTORS [17], [30]–[32]

Methods	Advantages	Limitations	Accuracy
Broken magnets and Demagnetization			
k-nearest neighbors (k-NN)	Simple, works with small data	Sensitive noise	Approx. 85-88 %
Autoencoder	Detects anomalies without labels	May miss precise	Approx. 90-93 %
Convolutional neural network (CNN)	Combines spatial and temporal features	Complex training	Approx. 97-99%
SVM	Classification Accuracy	Computational Complexity	93-97 %
Eccentricity Faults			
Vibration + SVM	High Classification Accuracy	Requires multiple sensors	Approx. 88-92 %
Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)	High accuracy in image-based vibration analysis	Needs labeled data	Approx. 95-98 %
Generative Adversarial Network(GAN)	Generates rare fault data	Training instability	Approx. 93-96%
Imbalance and Misalignment Faults			
Vibration + SVM	Reduce the dimensions and extract features	Difficult to classify the defected data	Approx. 98 %
Deep residual shrinkage network	high diagnostic accuracy	Complexity	Approx. 84.09%–86.51 %

PMSMs have attracted considerable research interest because of their essential role in predictive maintenance and fault diagnosis. Because PMSMs are widely used in many different applications, it is necessary to have strong condition monitoring systems in place to improve operational dependability and reduce unscheduled downtime. PMSM diagnostic systems employ AI methods such as neural networks, fuzzy logic, and expert systems for fault detection and health monitoring. Reference [14] emphasizes the application of intelligent diagnostic methods that leverage these technologies to effectively detect and classify stator winding faults via continuous monitoring of stator current waveforms [33], [34]. The scholars demonstrate that advanced machine learning algorithms enhance diagnostic accuracy and optimize maintenance processes, ultimately reducing operational costs and downtime [14].

Artificial intelligence enhances traditional condition monitoring by enabling automated, intelligent, predictive diagnostics based on sensor data. The following are the key strategies integrated with AI techniques: Vibration-Based Condition Monitoring, Current and Voltage Analysis, Thermal and Acoustic Monitoring, and AI-Driven Predictive Maintenance Frameworks [31].

A. Machine Learning-Based Vibration Condition Monitoring.

Vibration-based monitoring is a reliable diagnostic approach for detecting rotor failures in PMSMs. This methodology employs the analysis of vibration signals to detect mechanical faults, including imbalance, eccentricity, defective bearings, demagnetization, misalignment, bearing faults, and rotor defects. The vibration patterns generated during the operation of PMSMs provide essential insights into the overall health of the motor [35]. In reference [36], a method combining Process Power Spectrum Entropy with Support Vector Machines (SVM) was developed to effectively diagnose rotor vibration faults. Their experiments demonstrated significant improvements in precision, generalization, and robustness, highlighting its potential for real-time monitoring applications in PMSMs [36]. Similarly, reference [37] emphasized the importance of recurrence quantification analysis for diagnosing faults in rotor systems, noting that deviations in vibration signatures can indicate the onset of mechanical issues [37].

B. Current and Voltage Analysis

The current and voltage analysis method is employed to identify faults in PMSMs, including demagnetization and inter-turn faults. Machine learning has successfully detected demagnetization faults through stator current analysis. In reference [14], the authors implemented machine learning-based condition monitoring models to detect partial demagnetization of rotor permanent magnets, utilizing techniques such as k-nearest neighbors (KNN) and multi-layer perceptron (MLP) to evaluate and compare automated fault detection performance. To extract features related to PM faults from the stator phase current signal, short-time Fourier transform (STFT) was employed for time-frequency domain analysis. Commonly used ML algorithms in this context include CNN, SVM, artificial neural ANN, and Random Forest.

C. Thermal and Acoustic Monitoring

Thermal and acoustic monitoring of the PMSMs is essential for assessing the conditions of the permanent magnets and stator windings. Sensor-based monitoring methods utilize direct temperature measurement via thermally sensitive devices. Automated monitoring systems have been developed to detect uniform demagnetization faults, using data-driven approaches to enhance fault diagnosis [pietrzak 'demagnetization' 2023-1, [38]. These systems combine acoustic and thermal information to deliver a holistic assessment of motor condition, allowing timely interventions and maintenance [38]. The integration of artificial intelligence in these systems further improves their ability to predict and diagnose faults, enhancing the reliability of PMSM drive systems [pietrzak 'demagnetization' 2023-1, [39].

D. AI-based Predictive Maintenance Components

The main components of AI-based Predictive Maintenance are [40]:

- Data collection:
Internet of Things (IoT) devices/sensors: Sensors collect

real-time information, including variables of temperature, pressure, and electrical current, that provides critical insights into motor conditions and supports predictive maintenance analysis. Data Loggers: Capture and transmit real-time data. Computerized Maintenance Management Systems (CMMS): Store maintenance history, parts usage, and standard operating procedures for efficient maintenance tracking and planning.

- Data processing: Involves cleaning, normalizing, and handling missing values in raw sensor data to ensure accuracy and consistency for effective predictive maintenance analysis.
- AI algorithms: Artificial intelligence methodologies, including deep neural networks and statistical learning techniques, form the computational core of predictive maintenance architectures.
- Prediction and Decision-making Modules: Failure Probability Estimation: Assess the timing and likelihood of potential system or component failures. Remaining Useful Life (RUL) Estimation: Estimate the duration in which a component can continue to function effectively before failure. Maintenance scheduling: Plan maintenance activities to ensure timely intervention and efficient use of resources.
- Communication and Integration: Ensure that system insights are shared with stakeholders such as maintenance teams and management to drive effective action.
- User Interface and Reporting: Provides dashboards and visual tools that help maintenance staff and decision-makers interpret complex data and generate well-informed decisions.

V. FUTURE TRENDS AND RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Monitoring conditions and diagnosing faults in PMSMs are undergoing a significant transformation, particularly with the integration of AI techniques. Future trends and research on rotor faults in PMSMs should prioritize predictive maintenance through advanced AI methodologies, while also addressing the unique challenges presented by various types of faults. Rotor related faults, including demagnetization and eccentricity, are of significant concern. The precise detection of these faults is essential, as their neglect can result in diminished efficiency and potential operational failure [14]. The incorporation of machine learning algorithms into condition monitoring systems is essential for improving the diagnosis of rotor faults. For instance, methodologies utilizing SVMs and CNNs show significant potential in identifying the spectral signatures linked to demagnetization faults in PMSMs [25]. The AI-based techniques are capable of analyzing operational data to detect anomalies that may signify impending failure, thereby facilitating preventive interventions [41].

The emphasis on automated monitoring systems that provide real-time diagnostics of rotor faults signifies a prominent trend within the field. Technologies employing Hall-effect sensors facilitate continuous online monitoring, thereby enabling the ongoing assessment of rotor and load defects during

the operation of PMSMs [4], [41]. Nevertheless, dependence on individual sensors poses a risk of failure; therefore, the development of robust fault-tolerant systems is essential [2]. AI algorithms, particularly those employed in predictive analysis, can enhance the interpretation of sensor data, thereby improving the consistency and reliability of fault detection mechanisms [15]. Significant research directions focus on the refinement of AI algorithms to enhance fault classification and diagnosis within dynamic operational conditions. For example, the advancement of deep learning frameworks presents an opportunity to more accurately model and predict fault scenarios through training on extensive datasets derived from real-time PMSM operation. This advancement can enhance the accuracy and precision of fault diagnosis, supporting a shift toward more comprehensive condition-monitoring approaches [25].

The future of rotor fault diagnosis in PMSMs through AI-driven condition monitoring is promising. Future research should focus on enhancing machine learning models for better fault identification and diagnostics, as well as developing robust monitoring solutions for dynamic industrial environments.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a comprehensive review of the current state of research regarding rotor faults in PMSMs, specifically emphasizing machine learning methodologies for diagnosis and condition monitoring. The study evaluates the most recent artificial intelligence-based fault diagnostic approaches, with a particular focus on rotor failures in PMSMs. Common rotor faults identified in PMSMs include demagnetization, eccentricity, imbalance, and misalignment. AI and ML algorithms enhance fault detection, improving the reliability and performance of PMSMs. Recent research suggests that the effective detection and diagnosis of rotor faults require comprehensive monitoring techniques that integrate data-driven methodologies. However, there are a limited number of studies focused on AI-based condition monitoring and fault diagnosis specifically for PMSM rotor faults. The integration of artificial intelligence into fault diagnosis and monitoring processes has been shown to reduce maintenance costs and motor downtime while simultaneously enhancing productivity and operational efficiency.

Recent research indicates that various traditional techniques for detecting and diagnosing faults in PMSMs have been implemented. However, the application of artificial intelligence in electrical machines is still necessary. This review highlights a limited number of studies focusing on condition monitoring and artificial intelligence related to rotor faults in PMSMs. The study highlights the necessity for further exploration of AI integration in monitoring PMSM conditions and diagnosing faults.

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